

Thermal binder removal from large ceramic parts 3D printed by the digital light processing method

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Abstract

This paper investigates the size limit for defect-free binder removal from 3D printed bodies produced using a commercial alumina suspension by the digital light processing method. Binder removal from cylindrical bodies with a diameter of 5 mm, 9 mm, 11 mm, and 15 mm was carried out in two different debinding atmospheres (nitrogen and air) using various heating schedules. In the nitrogen atmosphere, the binder could be removed without defects from bodies with a diameter of 15 mm. In contrast, bodies with a diameter of only 5 mm were prepared defect-free in the air atmosphere. Thermoanalytical methods and microstructural analyses were applied to explain the observed differences in binder removal and defect formation. The debinding mechanisms were proposed, and the critical steps for defect-free processing were identified and discussed.

Keywords

3D printing, Binder removal, Microstructure, Size limit, Cracking

1. Introduction

Additive manufacturing (AM) of ceramics, also known as ceramic three-dimensional (3D) printing, is experiencing a huge interest in both academic and industrial communities because of promising results in the production of high-performance ceramic components with geometrically complex architectures, which are difficult to process using classical processing

methods [1-3]. Among the various AM technologies, vat polymerization methods, e.g., stereolithography (SLA) or digital light processing (DLP), are considered to be the most promising technologies due to their excellent feature resolution and quality of the final parts [4]. Regardless of the vat-polymerization method, the photopolymerization of photosensitive resins with dispersed ceramic particles is the essential processing step [5]. After illuminating the photosensitive ceramic suspension with a light source of appropriate wavelength, a complex polymeric network is formed, and liquid ceramic suspension is transformed into a solid layer. As the layers are stacked on top of each other, the final 3D part is created. The 3D-printed ceramic part is then composed of ceramic particles anchored in a polymeric network [6]. Before the high-temperature densification of the particle compact, the polymeric network and all other organic additives must be removed in a separate binder removal (debinding) step. The removal of the polymeric network is often the most critical step of the process chain. Although many debinding methods have been developed in ceramics processing, thermal binder removal [7, 8] is almost solely used for photopolymerized 3D printed parts. This step usually takes more time than printing itself and often results in defect formation [9]. Once the defects are created in the body during the debinding process, their healing during sintering is not probable, and the defects are usually exaggerated during sintering. The debinding problems are especially pronounced in the case of large solid bodies [10, 11].

The mechanisms of thermal debinding include thermal degradation of the polymeric network, diffusion of degradation products and other low-molecular-weight binder additives to the body surface (or binder/atmosphere interface), and their evaporation. In the air atmosphere, an additional degradation mechanism, namely oxidative degradation, is involved. The sudden gas evolution during boiling of low molecular weight components and degradation products in the pores filled with a liquid/solid binder is considered to be the main cause of defect formation during thermal debinding [12]. The easiest way to prevent defect formation is to slow the heating rate, especially in the temperature regions with the highest mass loss rate.

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) and differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) of the printed material are commonly used to adjust the heating profile of the binder removal [12]. Recent reports also showed the importance of a debinding atmosphere. Many authors reported stronger internal stresses and more serious defect formation during debinding in an air atmosphere than in non-oxidizing atmospheres of Ar [9], 95 % Ar + 5 % H₂ [13], or N₂ [14]. Zhang et al. [15] compared the effect of different aerobic and anaerobic atmospheres and vacuum on defect formation during debinding. The vacuum minimized the number of defects in the bodies after debinding and provided a higher sintered density. A higher sintered density after debinding in the vacuum compared with debinding in the air was also confirmed in another study by Wu et al. [16]. Zhou et al. [17] proposed a two-step process with vacuum debinding followed by air debinding. The vacuum prevented abrupt gas formation, and

subsequent air debinding removed all remaining carbon residues. Unfortunately, most of these articles did not satisfactorily explain the effect of debinding atmospheres. The discussion about the underlying mechanisms of debinding in different atmospheres was either missing, or the explanation was highly hypothetical without experimental proof [15, 18]. Another approach to preventing high peaks of weight loss rate during debinding is to add a non-reactive diluent to the binder system. This compound is not involved in the photopolymerization reaction and, due to its lower molecular weight, can be removed prior to the main decomposition of the polymeric network. The removal of a non-reactive diluent can facilitate the formation of open pores and interconnected channels, thus providing shorter pathways for the subsequent discharge of degradation products from the decomposed polymer network. This strategy resembles the debinding of a multicomponent binder in ceramic injection molding [19-21]. Moreover, the non-reactive diluent can also act as a plasticizer, controlling the rheological properties of the ceramic suspension, reducing photopolymerization shrinkage, and weakening the internal stresses by decreasing the crosslinked density of the polymeric network. The successfully applied non-reactive diluents include dibutyl phthalate [22], polyethylene glycols (PEG 200 [23] and PEG 400 [24]), or polypropylene glycol (PPG 400)[18]. Non-reactive diluents with even lower molecular weight (butoxyethyl acetate [25] and diethylene glycol [26]) were used when the removal temperature of PEG 400 coincided with the removal temperature of the main binder.

This investigation aimed to describe the effect of a heating profile and debinding atmosphere on the size limit for defect-free binder removal from bodies printed by the DLP method. In this work, we tried to reveal and explain the main differences in debinding mechanisms in air and inert atmospheres and to correlate them with the maximum available size of the defect-free bodies after debinding.

2. Experimental

2.1. 3D printing of test bodies

The alumina bodies were prepared using a DLP printer (CeraFab S65, Lithoz GmbH, Austria) and a commercially available alumina-based photocurable suspension (Lithalox 350, Lithoz GmbH, Austria). The test bodies were printed in the shape of a cylinder with a constant height of 15 mm and a diameter of 5 mm, 9 mm, 11 mm, and 15 mm. The printing was performed with an exposure energy of 150 mJ cm^{-2} , a layer thickness of $25 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$, and a light intensity of 50 mW cm^{-2} . The system provides a lateral pixel resolution of $40 \times 40 \text{ }\mu\text{m}^2$, enabling the production of ceramic bodies with high dimensional accuracy and surface quality. All printing parameters were selected based on the material manufacturer's recommendations to ensure optimal curing and printing behavior.

2.2. Thermal analysis of printed bodies

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) and differential thermal analysis (DTA) of the printed bodies were performed using a TGA/DTA analyzer (96 Line TGA - DTA/DSC, Setaram, France) at a heating rate of $1\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C min}^{-1}$ up to a temperature of $800\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ in nitrogen and air ($80\% \text{N}_2 + 20\% \text{O}_2$) atmospheres with a gas flow of 50 ml min^{-1} . Tests were performed with three sizes of samples that were cut from the largest printed cylinder: crushed sample (crushed in a mortar), small sample (body volume of $\sim 45\text{ mm}^3$), and large sample (body volume of $\sim 90\text{ mm}^3$).

2.3. Debinding and sintering of cylindrical test bodies

The samples for the binder removal were used as printed without any additional pretreatment before debinding. Debinding experiments were performed in both air and nitrogen atmospheres. During air debinding, the ceramic bodies were placed on a ceramic plate. The air debinding was performed in a static atmosphere. During the nitrogen debinding, the bodies were embedded in granular activated carbon (AY-5 12x30, Carbon Link, UK). The nitrogen flow of 20 L h^{-1} was maintained during the binder removal in the muffle furnace. Two debinding schedules with different heating rates (long and short) were applied, as shown in Fig. 1(a). The long schedule in the air atmosphere was recommended by the producer of the ceramic suspension for large bodies. Both debinding schedules were tested under the air and nitrogen atmospheres, i.e., four variants of debinding experiments were conducted. Ten samples of each size were used for each debinding experiment. All samples, after debinding, were sintered in air at 1650°C using the schedule given in Fig. 1(b).

In addition, the debinding of cylinders with a diameter of 15 mm using the short debinding schedule in nitrogen or air atmospheres was interrupted at various temperatures ($150\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $200\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $250\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $300\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, and $350\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) to investigate their internal structure and monitor the progress of binder removal.

Fig. 1 Heating schedule for (a) debinding and (b) sintering of printed samples.

2.4. Characterization methods

The macro defects and cracks in the printed samples were checked using an optical microscope before and after debinding. After sintering, the samples were inspected optically again, and the density of the sintered samples was measured in water using the Archimedes method. The relative densities were calculated using a theoretical density (t.d.) of 3.987 g cm^{-3} for alumina. The macrostructure of the samples after partial debinding was analyzed using a stereomicroscope (Stemi 508, Zeiss, Germany), and the microstructure of the green bodies and bodies after partial debinding was analyzed using a scanning electron microscope (SEM) (Verios 460L, FEI, Czech Republic). For the SEM investigation of as-printed samples and samples after partial debinding, the cross section of the samples was ion beam polished under cryogenic conditions ($-120 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, 6kV, 3 mA) using an ion beam milling system (EM TIC 3X, Leica, Germany). The sintered samples were mechanically polished for the SEM analysis. All samples for electron microscopy were carbon-coated using 15 nm of carbon (AM ACE 600, Leica, Germany)

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Thermal analysis

Fig. 2(a) shows mass losses during the heating of the printed bodies in nitrogen and air atmospheres. The oxygen in the air atmosphere caused the shift of mass loss curves to lower temperatures compared with nitrogen. A pronounced effect of sample size was observed during debinding in the air. The mass loss curves of bigger samples were moved to higher temperatures, closer to the mass loss curves of samples treated in nitrogen. On the other hand, only negligible differences between samples of different sizes were found during debinding in nitrogen. After debinding in the nitrogen atmosphere, carbon residues from the organic binder and other additives (about 1% of the total mass) remained in the body structure. Fig. 2(b) gives the thermal effect of debinding in different atmospheres. The thermal degradation occurring in nitrogen resulted in almost no thermal effects. On the other hand, the oxidative

Fig. 2 Thermal analysis of the printed samples showing (a) thermogravimetric curves and (b) heat flow curves.

degradation occurring in air exhibited three exothermic peaks. These peaks correspond to the steps with steep mass losses (see Fig. 3). With the increasing sample size, the mass loss below 200 °C rapidly decreased, and the first low-temperature exothermic peak decreased. The other two exothermic peaks increased as the mass loss was moved to higher temperatures in the large sample.

Fig. 3 Comparison of the temperature position of peaks on heat flow curves and derivative thermogravimetric curves.

3.2. Debinding defects

A set of cylindrical bodies with different diameters after debinding in nitrogen are shown in Fig. 4. Tables 1 and 2 show the percentage of defect-free bodies after debinding in nitrogen and air, respectively. It is obvious that debinding in the nitrogen atmosphere was more successful than in the air atmosphere. Debinding in nitrogen using the long schedule provided all bodies defect-free. Debinding in nitrogen using the short schedule also provided defect-

Fig. 4 Set of printed cylinders after debinding in the nitrogen atmosphere.

free bodies, except for the largest cylinders with a diameter of 15 mm. On the other hand, debinding in the air was completely successful only when using the long schedule for cylinders with a diameter of 5 mm. In all other cases, cracks appeared in several or often in all samples. The typical debinding defect is shown in Fig. 5. This was a partial or full crack through the cylindrical sample along the printing layers. Table 1 and Table 2 also show the

Table 1 Relative sintered density and percentage of defect-free sintered bodies after debinding in nitrogen

N_2 Cylinder diameter (mm)	Long debinding schedule			Short debinding schedule		
	Relative density (% t.d.)	SD* (% t.d.)	Defect-free (%)	Relative density (% t.d.)	SD* (% t.d.)	Defect-free (%)
5	97.58	0.13	100	97.28	0.18	100
9	95.98	0.20	100	96.06	0.18	100
11	95.55	0.10	100	95.51	0.18	100
15	94.42	0.22	100	94.67	0.25	80

*SD = sample standard deviation of relative density

Table 2 Relative sintered density and percentage of defect-free sintered bodies after debinding in air

<i>Air</i> Cylinder diameter (mm)	Long debinding schedule			Short debinding schedule		
	Relative density (% t.d.)	SD* (% t.d.)	Defect-free (%)	Relative density (% t.d.)	SD* (% t.d.)	Defect-free (%)
5	97.31	0.24	100	97.40	0.31	80
9	96.33	0.19	70	96.66	0.23	0
11	96.03	0.34	20	96.26	0.24	0
15	95.50	0.40	0	95.55	0.32	0

*SD = sample standard deviation of relative density

Fig. 5 Cross-section of a sintered cylinder with a typical crack after debinding in air.

relative densities of sintered ceramic bodies. The sintered densities were similar for bodies processed in nitrogen using long and short debinding schedules and decreased with the increasing cylinder diameter from 97.6 % t.d. to 94.4 % t.d. The densities of bodies processed in air were similar to those processed in nitrogen. The slightly higher densities achieved in larger cylinders processed in air compared to nitrogen could result from cracking. The fully cracked parts behaved as individual smaller bodies during the remaining debinding and sintering and reached a density corresponding to these smaller bodies.

3.3. Structure characterization

Fig. 6 shows photographs of longitudinal and transverse sections of cylindrical bodies with a diameter and height of 15 mm after debinding to different temperatures in nitrogen and air. This figure shows a clear difference between bodies treated in nitrogen (Fig. 6(a)) and air (Fig. 6(b)). In the nitrogen atmosphere, the bodies turned slightly grey homogeneously throughout the entire volume during debinding. After debinding in the air atmosphere, we could observe a layer of brownish-grey products of oxidative degradation, which grew with the debinding temperature from the surface to the center of the bodies. Moreover, the photos of transverse sections of the cylindrical bodies show that the binder degradation and removal were microscopically inhomogeneous, i.e., a debinding inhomogeneity was observed in the volume of a printed layer. Because the transversal cut was not perfectly perpendicular to the cylinder axis (i.e., not perfectly parallel with the 25 μm-thick printed layers), color strips

Fig. 6 Longitudinal and transverse sections of cylindrical bodies with a diameter and height of 15 mm after debinding to different temperatures in (a) nitrogen and (b) air using the short schedule.

Fig. 7 Binder mass loss during debinding of cylindrical bodies with a diameter and height of 15 mm after debinding to different temperatures in nitrogen and air.

demonstrate cross sections of more or less degraded parts of the printed layers. This phenomenon could be clearly observed during air debinding due to the brownish-grey degradation products, but it was also observed in bodies treated in nitrogen. The graph in Fig. 7 shows binder losses of the investigated cylindrical bodies (with 15 mm in diameter) in different atmospheres. The air atmosphere sped up the binder removal compared to nitrogen. To compare structures with the same binder loss in air and nitrogen, we must compare bodies heated to different temperatures, e.g., the binder loss of ~40% was reached at a temperature of 250°C in air and 300°C in nitrogen.

To better understand the debinding mechanisms, we investigated the microstructure of bodies after partial debinding. Figs. 8 and 9 show the microstructure of green printed bodies, which can serve as a standard for comparison with bodies after partial binder removal. Fig. 8 shows a cross-section of the green body with printed layers of 25 μm in thickness. The interface between layers can be clearly observed, which means that these interfaces create a certain structural inhomogeneity in the body structure. Fig. 9 shows a detailed view of the microstructure. The white arrows mark the interface between the printed layers. The printed layers consisted of dispersed ceramic particles and a binder that fully filled the pores between the particles. The interface between the layers showed discontinuity in regular particle packing but without any voids or air bubbles.

Fig. 10 shows microstructures of a body after debinding to 250 °C in the air atmosphere (with a binder loss of ~40 %). A porous structure with a porosity gradient in the printed layer was found near the body surface (see Fig. 10(a)). The difference in the porosity was visible at the printed layer interface. A similar structure, but with a smaller overall porosity, could also

Fig. 8 SEM micrograph of the green sample structure. (The image was created in the backscatter electron mode.)

Fig. 9 Detailed SEM micrograph of a green sample structure. (The image was created in the secondary electron mode.) The arrows mark the interface between printed layers.

be found in the center of the body (see Fig. 10(c)). However, a substantially reduced porosity was found in the microstructure near the edge of the brownish-grey layer (see Fig. 10(b)). The porosity at this position decreased through the printed layer from a moderate porosity to an almost fully dense structure similar to the printed green bodies. The important finding from this observation is that the overall porosity at the edge of the brownish-grey layer was probably lower than in the center of the body. The investigated structure of the body after debinding in air to 250 °C can be compared with the structure of a body after debinding in nitrogen. Fig. 11 shows the microstructures of the body after debinding to 250 °C in nitrogen. The binder loss in nitrogen was lower than in air (25 % vs 40 %). This structure was similar to the structure of printed green bodies but with several isolated pores. There was an apparent

porosity gradient between the surface and the center of the body, as well as inside the individual printed layers. No intermediate structure was observed, as was the case with air.

Fig. 10 SEM micrographs of the body structure after debinding to 250 °C in air taken (a) near the body surface, (b) at the edge of the brownish-grey layer, and (c) in the body center. The optical photograph shows the exact position of the observed microstructures in the body cross section.

Fig. 11 SEM micrographs of the body structure after debinding to 250 °C in nitrogen taken (a) near the body surface and (b) in the body center.

Fig. 12 SEM micrographs of the body structure after debinding to 300 °C in nitrogen taken (a) near the body surface and (b) in the body center.

Fig. 12 shows the microstructures of the body after debinding to 300 °C in nitrogen. After debinding to this temperature in nitrogen, we obtained similar binder loss as in air debinding to 250 °C (~40 %). The SEM images show a porous structure with no apparent porosity difference between the surface and the body center. The porosity gradient inside the individual layers also decreased substantially. It was found that in all debinding cases, the least porous part of the printed layer (the darker area in the SEM images and brownish-grey area in optical images) was at the side of the layer surface that was directly exposed to the polymerizing light. A micrograph of the sintered structure is shown in Fig. 13. After sintering at 1650°C for 2 h, 2.5-4.5 % of porosity remained in the ceramics, depending on the body size. Nevertheless, no signs of interfaces between layers can be observed.

Fig. 13 SEM micrograph of the structure of printed ceramics sintered at 1650 °C.

4. Discussion

It is well known that oxidative degradation of organic polymers has a lower activation energy than thermal degradation and can be active at lower temperatures [27]. Therefore, the mass losses in air can be realized at lower temperatures than in nitrogen, where only thermal degradation occurs. The air oxygen must diffuse into the organic binder during the oxidative degradation, and the products of the oxidative degradation must diffuse out of the body to evaporate. The increasing diffusion path limits the extent of oxidative degradation. Thus, the decreasing specific surface area of bigger samples decreases the contribution of oxidative degradation to the total mass losses during debinding, as shown in Fig. 2. Moreover, oxidative degradation of the binder system occurs in several steps (see Fig. 3) through stable intermediate products. The brownish-grey layer growing from the surface to the body center represents the formation of the stable intermediate products of oxidative degradation (see Fig. 6). The oxidative intermediate products remain in the structure and “seal” the structure, as shown in Fig. 10(b). Further oxidation and removal of the stable intermediate products only

occur at temperatures of 300-350 °C (see Fig. 3). At this temperature, however, thermal degradation is already active in the whole volume of the body. We hypothesize that the stable oxidative intermediate products prevent the diffusion of emerging volatile products of the thermal degradation (and other possible low molecular weight binder components) to the surface and their evaporation. Thermal degradation products thus gasify inside the body, and the gas pressure causes cracks along layer interfaces, which are the weakest points of the body. The present research suggests that air debinding can be beneficial for thin-walled bodies (< 5 mm) as it accelerates binder removal, but is unsuitable for thicker-walled bodies due to the formation of cracks. In the nitrogen atmosphere, the maximum wall thickness that can be prepared defect-free depends on the ability of the low molecular degradation products to diffuse to the body surface (or to the nearest binder/atmosphere interface) and evaporate. The diffusion must be quick enough to prevent reaching a critical concentration of low molecular components, resulting in boiling and gas evolution inside the body.

The proposed debinding mechanism resembles the binder removal described in bodies with a thermoplastic binder [19, 20]. The main difference lies in the crosslinked structure of the polymer binder in 3D printed bodies. Unlike the viscous polymer melts in thermoplastic ceramic mixtures, there is a limited possibility of binder redistribution during debinding in 3D printed bodies. One of the key features of the thermal removal of crosslinked binders from 3D printed bodies is the formation of pores in a fully saturated structure in the body center, as confirmed in the microstructure images in Fig. 11. This phenomenon is highly unfavorable in structures with viscous polymer melts. It can be expected that the pore formation inside the saturated body can accelerate the transport of low molecular components to the body surface, especially once the pores become interconnected. Another unique feature of the present printed bodies is the porosity inhomogeneity in the individual printed layers during debinding. It is supposed that the surface of the layer exposed to the polymerizing light has the highest polymer conversion, i.e., the highest crosslinking density. The light energy and, thus, the degree of polymer conversion decrease exponentially with the distance from the light-exposed surface [28]. It means that there is a different crosslinking density through the layer thickness. Lower crosslinking density results in a higher amount of unreacted monomers. These low molecular components (unreacted monomers and other low molecular binder components) can more easily diffuse in the less crosslinked structure to the surface and create pores before massive thermal degradation of the crosslinked polymer network occurs (see Fig. 3). Once thermal degradation of crosslinked polymer network is initiated, the porosity inhomogeneity in the printed layer decreases and finally diminishes (see Fig. 12). Although the individual printed layers and their interfaces played an important role in the binder removal, this inhomogeneity was eliminated during sintering and a fully homogeneous and isotropic microstructure was obtained, as shown in Fig. 13.

5. Conclusions

This study investigated the influence of the debinding atmosphere and heating schedule on defect formation during the thermal debinding of alumina bodies fabricated by the digital light processing method. The results demonstrated that the maximum size of defect-free body was strongly dependent on the debinding atmosphere. The nitrogen atmosphere allowed for successful debinding of parts up to 15 mm in diameter, while the air atmosphere limited defect-free debinding to 5 mm samples. The crack formation in air was attributed to the oxidative degradation of the binder, which proceeded from the surface to the body center and produced stable intermediates that hindered uniform binder removal. Prolonging the heating schedule increased the maximum size of defect-free bodies but could not fully counteract the effects of oxidative degradation. The structure and density of sintered bodies were not affected by the conditions of binder removal.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Premysl Stastny: Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal Analysis, Investigation, Writing - original draft. **Ondrej Man:** Formal analysis, Methodology. **Dominik Brouczek:** Investigation, Validation. **Martin Schwentenwein:** Investigation, Validation. **Martin Trunec:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Supervision, Writing - original draft, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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